

DEVELOPMENT OF FULL CF/PEEK(APC-2) HORIZONTAL STABILIZER MODELS AND THEIR STRENGTH TEST RESULTS

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ABSTRACT

Horizontal Stabilizer models made of CF/Thermoplastic (CF/PEEK:APC-2) composite system are developed as the final step of an effort for its application in NAL program. Impact damage is given first to each model. Simulated fatigue loads for some levels of flights are applied to one of the model. Ultrasonic C-scan inspection after fatigue loadings reveals that no delamination growth is observed at all. Any other symptom of material damage is not found at all by AE hit trace and strain records. The residual static strength test of this model reveals excellent load bearing capacity of CF/PEEK structure. This result implies a potential for the weight reduction ratio of around 35% to the baseline metallic structure.

INTRODUCTION

Weight reduction is the most important goal for aircraft structural engineers and researchers. A state-of-the-art reduction ratio by CF/Epoxy composite system is considered to be around 20% and it is not fully satisfactory. CF/thermoplastic composite systems, particularly CF/PEEK, exhibit a great potential for this goal due to their excellent damage and fatigue tolerant properties. NAL is conducting a long term effort for verification and application of CF/PEEK to aircraft structures as one of the special research programs. In this program, excellent fatigue properties in coupon level [1], high CAI strengths of thick plates and stiffened panels [2] have been clarified well. In order to obtain those favorable properties, fabrication process must be established first [3] in which an intrinsic difficulty of CF/PEEK due to its hardness in prepreg has been overcome. It took a long time to establish the process and this part of the technology is always accumulated in the partner company, Fuji Heavy Industries (FHI) Co. LTD, during the research program. Based upon these foundations, two wing box models of full CF/PEEK for a horizontal stabilizer of conceptual aircraft are built as the final article and tested in spectrum fatigue loads simulating real flights. The residual static strength test accompanies those fatigue tests. The present paper reports some essential findings in the experimental procedures, results and numerical predictions.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE MODEL

The models are designed so as to meet requirements of a horizontal stabilizer (H-Stab) of a conceptual medium-sized commercial jet transport. This aircraft is still in the level of a plan.

Since the model simulates an outboard portion of the H-Stab, it is considered to be rather thin as for the primary structure. A model background and its structural concept is shown in Fig.1. Its span is roughly 90cm mainly due to the fabrication cost. It is assembled with six major components using mechanical fasteners. Upper and lower panels are fabricated by a fusion bonding method [3] for joining a skin and three T-stiffeners. PEEK film is used for bonding agent. For establishing this fabrication technology, a lasting effort and funding was required as stated. Protection pads made of 22 ply CF/Epoxy with tapered edges are glued after the panel completion on top and bottom surfaces of root and tip ends of the box for attachment of supporting and loading steel fixtures. I-spars are also fusion-bonded with pre-formed UD-prepreg plies. Ribs are secondarily formed by heat with flat plates and trimmed. Two boxes were fabricated actually FHI LTD. A picture of the model before an assembly of the loading and supporting steel fixtures is shown in Fig.2.

Figure 1 Background and Concept of the Model

Figure 2 Picture of the Model before Fixture Assembly

IMPACT TESTS PRIOR TO LOADINGS

One significant goal of the present program is to examine a damage tolerant performance of CF/PEEK structure. Recent test philosophy in the composite tail box programs [4,5] is also followed here. Therefore, an impact delamination damage is created in each box prior to loading. Pictures of the impact tests are shown in Fig.3. The used machine is a drop-weight type impactor, Dynatup GRC 8250. Impact head is a hemisphere of 12.5mm in diameter. Many impacts were given first to a spare stiffened panel on the skin-stiffener bonding region to determine relationships between normalized impact energy by the thickness and the delamination area. Visibility of impact dents is also checked. In these preliminary impacts, the panel is directly placed on a thick steel test bed with 4 legs shown in Fig.3; Right. According to the determined relationships, the energy level is decided to 3.56 J/mm and the real impact test onto #2 box was executed. Note that #2 box was tested first and #1 next. The box is supported as shown in Fig.3;

Figure 3 Pictures of Impact Test for #2 Box
Left : Impact Head at Positioning
Right: Supporting Situation of the Box

Right. The impact point is 50mm outboard to the rib next to the supporting fixture and on the back of the middle stiffener as shown later in Fig.8. Delamination area is inspected by an ultrasonic C-scanner and the result is shown in Fig.4(a). Due to an insufficient rigidity of the rib and panel, unexpectedly large elastic deformation occurs and absorbs the impact energy. Thus, the created delamination is 40mm², much smaller than intended. Based on this finding, #1 box is impacted in the exactly same manner as the spare panel with the reduced energy level of 2.67 J/mm from #2. C-scope of #1 box delamination is shown in Fig.4(b) and roughly intended area of 765mm² is obtained. From the practical viewpoint, however, such a situation is considered to be a proof of excellent impact resistance of CF/PEEK wing box structure. For thin portion of real structure, impact might not cause a design critical in the case of CF/PEEK. In other words, #1 box test is regarded as relatively conservative structural CAI experiment to the realistic situation.

Figure 4 Ultrasonic C-Scope of Delamination
a):#2, b):#1 Models

LOADING AND SUPPORTING DEVICES

In accordance with the impact tests, #2 model is tested first. The model is loaded only by up and down forces for cantilever bending as shown in Fig.5. Twisting torque and forward-backward forces by aerodynamic drag are neglected in this program because it is not a real flight model. Figure 6 shows a picture during fatigue tests. The supporting fixture has also a function of extension for increasing and adjusting a bending moment at the critical section because the length of the model is not enough due to a cost. Bending force is introduced to the model through a rod by a hydraulic actuator, MTS 247.22 of 100kN capacity. rod forces are mostly tension. The impact is located in the lower skin so as to be subjected to critical compression stresses. Loading signals are generated in a control system, MTS T-RAC, under the defined load spectrum. Take a note that a dummy wing tip is attached to the model as shown in Fig.6.

Figure 5 Schema of Loading and Supporting

Figure 6 Picture of Fatigue Test

DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

The present data acquisition devices are basically divided into two systems. The first system is driven by a data logger, HP-3852A and 3853A, for 1 channel of load, 4 channels of

deflections and 220 channels of strains. A schematic diagram of the systems are indicated in Fig.7. The strain gages are glued mainly to the outer surfaces of CF/PEEK portion. Some inner gages are glued at a chance when the box is disassembled once. The most important gage map for the lower panel outer is indicated in Fig.8 where the location of the impact is also given.

Figure 7 Concept of Data Acquisition System

In all static tests, the whole channels are activated. Sampling rate is about 2 seconds for each channel in the static tests. In fatigue tests, 7 channels of higher strain outputs are selected and recorded with the load data at the specified interval of simulated loading packages in order to minimize data volume. Those intervals are short at the initial fatigue test stage. They are lengthened toward accumulated flight numbers, finally saturated at 5000 flights.

Figure 8 Strain Gage Map on Lower Panel Outside

The other data acquisition system is an AE data analyzer, PAC SPARTAN-AT system of 12 channels. One of the author (YH) has been accumulating technique and know-how of AE analysis for tests of composite structures [6,7] where an emphasis is placed on identification of AE source location during the tests.

Figure 9 Measured Stress Pattern by Infrared Stress Graphic System (ISGS) for Lower Panel under Constant Amplitude (20kN) Loading and Schematic Illustration about Scan Area

Based on such expertise, AE sensor arrangement and setting details are defined. The basic assumption checked first is that this box is almost continuous in acoustics sense. The detail of the analyzed AE data presentation is skipped in this paper and remained for a future chance.

Two other devices are also tried for stress and strain data measurement. An infrared stress graphic system (ISGS) is used [8] for direct stress measurement around the impact delamination area of #2 box. An example of the measured data is shown in Fig.9 where an illustration is also attached. Because constant amplitude loadings are intrinsically required for this measurement, a sequence of 20kN tension sine waves are extracted from the loading patterns. The total used cycles are canceled later in the actual fatigue spectrum. Due to small delamination area, it can not be clearly identified. The final device tried here is a fiber optics strain measurement system with extrinsic Fabry-Perot sensors. The detail remains to a future publication.

OUTLINE OF SIMULATED FLIGHT LOAD SPECTRUM

Table 1 Five Grades of Simulated Flight Loads

Simulated flight loads are well defined and standardized rather for main wings of aircraft like TWIST program. For horizontal stabilizers, however, standard spectrum itself or even its determination procedure is not well publicized. By following some reference data of forerunner commercial aircraft, the loading spectrum is defined in the present program. Flight load levels are divided into 5 groups denoted by A(lower) to E(higher) flights. E flight contains one design limit load within the sequence and appears one time in every 5000 flights. Appearance probability of A to D flights are determined as indicated in Table 1 where the ratios of the maximum loads to the limit in each level is also given. The sequence of A to D flight is determined in MTS T-RAC system so as to be a semi-random process. One flight

Flight Grade	Ratio of the Maximum Load in the Flight to Limit Load	Probability for Appearance
A	0.6800	0.7448
B	0.6970	0.2089
C	0.7756	0.0427
D	0.9106	0.0034
E	1.00	0.0002

consists of a sequence of loadings simulating taxing, take-off etc., and landing. One loading pattern is defined by a half sine wave with specified the initial and final load levels. Some examples of actual flight loads will be given later.

Table 2 Sequence of Tests for #2 Box

The level of limit load for #2 box is determined directly based on the detailed model design conducted by FHI Co. LTD. A pull-down force of 34.52 kN (3520 kgf) is defined as the limit. Ultimate force is of course 1.5 times of the limit, 51.78 kN. For #1 model, a level increase is considered for reflecting the results of #2 model.

- Site and Model Setup
- Loading and Data Acquisition System Setup
- Static Partial Loading for System Check
- Low Level Fatigue (1000 Flights)
- Limit Load Test and Strain Survey
- ◆ Fatigue Loadings for 1 Life (50000 Flights)
- Limit Load Test
- ◆ Fatigue Loadings for 1 Life (50000 Flights)
- Limit Load Test
- ◆ Extra Fatigue Loadings (20000 Flights)
- Ultrasonic Inspection
- System Check and Limit Load Test
- ◆ Residual Strength Test
- ◆ Fatigue Tests

TEST PROCEDURES

After the impact tests, test procedures were started for #2 model at March 1994. Partial load static test for system check and static limit load test for strain survey were also conducted prior to main fatigue tests as shown in Table 2. One lifetime of the target aircraft is assumed

as 50000 flights. Preliminary fatigue tests were also done for checking T-RAC abilities. In this step and early part of the following main fatigue tests, the average of load frequency was set to be low. Equivalent loadings to twice of the lifetime and more, about 120000 flight, were given mainly at an increased frequency of 1000 flight/day. In this rate, the real flight time is condensed into 1.5 minutes for A flight. The higher load flights mean the longer time. The box was unmounted and inspected by a robotic ultrasonic C-scanner after all fatigue loads. A static residual strength test is then conducted.

Figure 10 Load and Strain Records at the First Limit Load Test

EXAMPLES OF TEST DATA

Strain survey results at the first limit load test is given in Fig.10. Locations of lower panel strain gages 25 to 49 are indicated in Fig.8 where prefix UO is erased. Gages 7 and 18 are glued on the upper panel and their positions correspond to UO31 and UO48, respectively. Output #1 indicates the load in kgf. The maximum compression strain of 2900×10^{-6} appears near the root end of the lower outer skin on the spar flange and its absolute value is larger than the corresponding tension strain.

Figure 11 Example of Load and Strain Records at 48000 Flight in Total

Typical examples of fatigue tests are shown in Figs.11 and 12. Figure 11 depicts load and some selected strain histories in a load sequence including A, B, C and D flights after frequency increase. The maximum compression strain in the most dominant A flight is found to be about 1750×10^{-6} . Similar example for the severest E flight is shown in Fig.12. It takes 6.5 minutes to finish this flight. Note that all E flight load sequences are applied to #2 box under human control and data acquisition at every 5000 flight interval. Actual load profiles for each level flight could be understood by Figs.11 and 12.

Figure 12 Example of Load and Strain Records for E flight at 49000 flight in Total

Due to space shortage, demonstration of AE data is omitted here. Basically speaking, AE signals are mostly generated around fasteners and the impact damage is not a significant source. According to such

AE records and strain data, there is no indication of delamination growth or other type of material damage development at all. Ultrasonic C-scope taken after all fatigue tests supports this finding. So, the second model will be tested under slightly higher loading spectrum.

COMPARISON OF STRAIN DATA WITH NUMERICAL PREDICTIONS

Numerical calculations of the strain distribution in the model are conducted by a commercially available FEM code, NISA-II. Basic element used is a 4 node quadrilateral composite shell element which allows transverse shear deformation. In a root and tip fixture areas, hypothetical laminates with thick steel substrate are defined. The input elastic moduli of UD-CF/PEEK slightly adjusted from the authors' previous data [9] are listed in Table 3. Number of elements in the FEM model is 1162. Graphic outputs for 0° layer stress in the x-direction, the direction of the spar, are indicated for the lower panel in Fig.13 where the model is upside-down. An upward force corresponding to the limit load is assumed to act at the point of a small arrow. Strain predictions for the surface 45° layer of skin along the spar line are given in Fig.14(a). Because no graphic is available for strain data in NISA-II, auxiliary calculations on data file base are required. Experimental strains at the first limit tests are also plotted where filled and open circles correspond to two spar lines. They compare favorably with the prediction curve except for local root area. Data at the limit tests after all life fatigue loadings are indicated in Fig.14(b). The prediction curve is the same as (a) and open and filled triangles are again measured strains. An interesting fact that an agreement is improved after fatigue is found near the root pad-up in Fig.14(b). Local fitting phenomena around the pad-up edge during fatigue might be ascribed to the reason.

Table 3 Input Elastic Moduli of CF/PEEK Ply

E_L	E_T	G_{LT}	ν_L	G_{TT}
117.3	10.3	4.62	0.38	3.43 (Unit:GPa)

RESULTS OF RESIDUAL STRENGTH TEST

The final static test is done to examine the residual strength of the box. Key points in test

Figure 13 Predicted Stress (σ_x) Distribution by NISA-II in 0° Ply of Lower Skin

Figure 14 Comparison of Predicted Strain (ϵ_x) on Lower Spar Lines with Experimental Data; (a):before, (b):after Fatigue

procedures are: four steps between zero and the limit, one step to the ultimate load from limit at a rate of 2%/sec. with at least 3 second holding at the ultimate, and monotonic increase up to the failure at the same rate. The model failed finally at 93.2 kN, 270 % of the limit. This too high percentage is probably caused by conservative design allowables derived by the preliminary tests using specimens of imperfect quality. From another view, this high strength implies a possibility of 20% increase of design criticals. Hence, about 35% weight reduction from a baseline metal structure seems to be possible. Load-strain relationships are shown in Fig. 15. This figure indicates that local skin buckling occurred near the spar root. However, such buckling does not affect the final strength seriously. The detail of this test must be examined in the near future.

Figure 15 Load-Strain Relationships at the Final Residual Strength Test

CONCLUSIONS

Excellent fatigue and damage tolerance properties of full CF/PEEK wing box model are well verified and demonstrated. No delamination growth is identified through all the fatigue loadings by AE records and ultrasonic C-scan data. Good correlation between experimental and predicted strain distributions in the lower panel surface is achieved. In the final residual strength test, the model exhibits incredibly high load bearing capacity in spite of local buckling in the root region of the lower panel. A deviation between designed and experimental strengths is probably caused by conservative design criticals taken through interim quality specimens. This fact implies that a weight reduction ratio of 35% is not impossible by CF/PEEK aircraft structures.

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